

Cloud-Based E-Learning Model and Students' Academic Achievement in Biology Students in Mkpato Enin Local Government Area

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ABSTRACT: This study examined the effect of cloud-based e-learning model and students' academic achievement in Biology in Mkpato Enin Local Government Area, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. Two research questions and two corresponding hypotheses were formulated to guide the study. A quasi-experimental, pretest-posttest, non-randomized design was adopted for the study. The study population comprised 1,754 Biology students enrolled in the 16 public secondary schools in Mkpato Enin Local Government Area during the 2025/2026 academic session. A sample of 97 Senior Secondary School One students, from two intact classes, was selected using a simple random sampling technique. The instrument for data collection was the Biology Achievement Test on Photosynthesis (BAPT). The reliability of the instrument was determined using the Kuder-Richardson formula-20, with a coefficient of 0.86. Data were analyzed using mean and standard deviation to answer the research questions, while analysis of covariance was used to test the hypotheses at a 0.05 level of significance. The result showed that there is a significant difference in mean achievement scores of Biology students taught the concept of photosynthesis using cloud-based e-learning model and conventional teaching method. Students taught using cloud-based e-learning model performed significantly better than those taught with the conventional teaching method. Also, there is no significant difference in mean achievement scores of male and female students taught using cloud-based e-learning model and conventional teaching method. It was recommended, among others, that Biology teachers should adopt cloud-based e-learning model teaching method to enhance the teaching and learning of photosynthesis and other Biology concepts.

KEYWORDS: cloud-based, e-learning model, conventional teaching method, photosynthesis, academic performance, gender.

INTRODUCTION

Biology is a natural science subject that deals with the systematic study of plants, animals, and microorganisms, from the cellular level to the whole organism, and how they live and influence each other in the environment. It consists of various contents which varies from microscopic organisms to the biosphere general, encompassing the earth's surface and all living things. According to Etukakpan *et al.*, (2025) Biology is the study of living organisms, their functions and the processes that govern life on earth. It is also the scientific study of life as it have a broad scope with several unifying themes that tie it together as a single, coherent field (Hillis *et al.*, 2020). Moreso, Biology is the branch of science that primarily deals with the structure, function, growth, origin, evolution, and distribution of organisms. It classifies and describes organisms, their functions, how species came into existence, and the interactions they have with each other and with the natural environment (Olayinka & Ogundare, 2022).

However, the importance of Biology in the growth and development of any nation and its citizens cannot be overemphasized as it is a discipline that seems to be synergic with other disciplines such as physics, chemistry, medicine, pharmacy, geography, geology among others (Falemu, 2025) providing a solid foundation for students who wish to pursue courses such as medicine, pharmacy, nursing, biochemistry, biotechnology and agriculture in the tertiary institutions. Moreover, every core science student requires a credit in Biology at the O' level to gain admission into the University to study these courses (Etukakpan *et al.*, 2025). Biology as a science related subject place more emphasis on equipping students with the knowledge of relevant concepts and scientific skills. It aims at developing broadly applicable skills such as problem-solving, communication, critical thinking and objective reasoning abilities to enable students to prepare for the workplace self-sustainability in the world economy (FME, 2014). With the objective of the biology curriculum, students are expected to be useful and productive members of the society. Therefore, in order to achieve these Biology objectives, teachers should promote students to assume responsibility and control over their acquisition of knowledge and skills. Thus, making students to become masters of their learning by controlling and managing what, how, why and when they learn.

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Despite the utilitarian value of Biology curriculum towards the scientific and technological development of nations, the achievement of Nigerian students in senior secondary schools has consistently been poor in external examinations such as West African Senior School Certificate Examination (WASSCE). The West African Examination Council Chief Examiners' reports (WAEC, 2020-2025) confirm that students' achievement in Biology has been below expectation over the years. Many studies have been carried out in an attempt to establish the causes and possible solutions to this problem but not much has been achieved since biology students at the secondary level continued to achieve poorly. Some of such studies revealed as teacher' competence in teaching Biology, location of schools, students' and schools' characteristics, teaching strategies used by teachers among others have been found responsible for the low performance in external examinations (Codjoe, et al., 2024; Johnson, 2024).

In addition to the above, teaching methods has been a major factor militating against the improvement of students' academic achievement (Daniel, et al., 2024) which is due to the notion that most science teachers still employ the traditional method of instruction. Recent studies Babalola, et al., (2025); Amiris (2025) emphasizes that the persistent underachievement in science subjects calls for the rapid digital transformation across educational system globally through the need for innovative instructional models capable of supporting flexible, personalized, and scalable learning. Among these innovations, cloud-based e-learning models have emerged as a strategic response to the limitation of conventional learning management systems and traditional face-to-face instruction. Cloud-based e-learning model has been a game changer in education, benefiting learners who prefer using technology to access educational content.

Cloud-based e-learning model is the currently fashionable term used to describe diverse use of information and communications technologies to support and enhance learning, teaching and assessment from resource-based learning (in which students carry out face-to-face tasks supplemented by a range of online resources) to fully online courses (Oludipe, et al., 2014). Cloud based e-learning model is one of the most significant technologies which help schools and institutions to create a good learning environment with the help of internet. It is a low cost with minimum expenditure technology that tackle problems related to the technological issues faced by cloud vendors and users (Eljak, et al., 2023). It could be used as a tool to decongest students' population in schools, and therefore eliminate all forms of problem associated with overpopulation of students in our institutions of learning. Among the learning technologies, e-learning offers several benefits over conventional classroom-based learning. Its biggest advantages are the reduced cost since a physical environment is no longer required and therefore it can be used at any time and place for the convenience of the student (El Mhouthi, et al., 2018). It further promotes effective usage of resources, offering a dynamic scalability. Cloud-based e-learning model has made it easier to share resources, in particular, areas where the resources are limited. In incorporating cloud-based in a learning environment, it requires examining the integration of teaching resources and development of effective teaching systems. Students and learners need to understand the effective ways in which technology to share learning content easier and irrespective of their location.

According to Alajmi, *et al.*, (2017), cloud-based e-learning model makes it easier for students to learn using their devices of choice. In addition, it acts a backup of the data, providing students and educators with great control of the technology used in teaching and learning process. Wu and Plakhtii (2021) also asserted that the introduction of cloud-based e-learning model in teaching results in the advancement of the training content and can considerably improve students' academic achievement due to updated learning technologies, concepts, and tools. Also, Alam (2021) revealed that, cloud-based e-learning, adaptive e-learning, interactive online learning, among other e-learning models have a significant relationship on students' academic achievement when effectively introduced. Hence, this study sought to investigate more on the effect on cloud-based e-learning model and students' academic achievement in Biology irrespective of their gender. Gender is the socially constructed roles, behaviours, and expectations associated with being male or female (Umanah & Atabang, 2025). It is used to indicate the distinction between human beings on the basis of masculinity and femininity in relation to their expected role and how each perceive science learning.

Gender refers to the socially or culturally constructed characteristics and roles which are ascribed to males and females in any society (Sunday, et al., 2025). It is a psychological term describing behaviour and attributes expected of individuals based on being male or female (Umanah & Sunday, 2022). Gender is one of the factors that may influence students' academic achievement and has generated a lot of concern for educators (Onunkwo, *et al.*, 2025; Umanah & Akpan, 2024). While some studies suggest that male students achieve better in science subjects, others report no significant gender differences in academic achievement (Umanah & Sunday 2025; Umanah & Akpan, 2024; Sunday & Edet, 2024). Etukakpan *et al.*, (2025) asserted that there was no significant difference in the performance mean scores between male and female students taught the concept of cell structure. Others found no significant difference between male and female chemistry students' academic performance (Umanah & Akpan, 2024; Sunday et al., 2025a). With the contradictions on the influence of gender, this study therefore sought to further investigate the influence of gender on students' academic achievement when taught the concept of photosynthesis using cloud-based e-learning model.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Despite the utilitarian value of Biology curriculum towards the scientific and technological development of nations, the achievement of Nigerian students in senior secondary schools has consistently been poor in external examinations such as West African

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Examination (WAEC) among others. The West African Examination Council Chief Examiners' reports (WAEC, 2020-2025) confirm that students' achievement in Biology has been below expectation over the years. Many studies have been carried out in an attempt to establish the causes and possible solutions to this problem but not much has been achieved since Biology students at the secondary level continued to achieve poorly. Some of such studies reveals teacher' competence in teaching Biology, location of schools, students' and schools' characteristics, teaching strategies used by teachers among others have been found responsible for the low achievement in external examinations. In addition to the above, teaching strategies has been a major factor militating against the improvement of students' academic achievement which is due to the notion that most science teachers still employ the traditional method of instruction. Recent emphasize that the persistent underachievement in science subjects calls for the rapid digital transformation across educational system globally through the need for innovative instructional models capable of supporting flexible, personalized, and scalable learning. Among these innovations, cloud-based e-learning models have emerged as a strategic response to the limitation of conventional learning management systems and traditional face-to-face instruction. Cloud-based e-learning model has been a game changer in education, benefiting learners who prefer using technology to access educational content. Understanding these gaps and persistent achievement challenges provides the rationale for the present study. Therefore, this study sought to fill this gap by investigating the effect of cloud-based e-learning model and students' academic achievement in Biology in Mkpato Enin Local Government Area.

PURPOSE OF THE STUDY

The purpose of this study was to investigate the effect of cloud-based e-learning model and students' academic achievement in Biology in Mkpato Enin Local Government Area. Specifically, the study sought to

1. determine the difference in the mean achievement score of Biology students taught the concept of photosynthesis using Cloud-based e-learning model and those taught using conventional method.
2. determine the difference in the mean achievement score of male and female Biology students taught the concept of photosynthesis using Cloud-based e-learning model.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

The following research questions shall guide the study:

1. What is the difference in the mean achievement score of Biology students taught the concept of photosynthesis using cloud-based e-learning model and those taught using conventional method?
2. What is the difference in the mean achievement score of male and female Biology students taught the concept of photosynthesis using cloud-based e-learning model?

HYPOTHESES

1. There is no significant difference in the mean achievement score of students taught the concept of photosynthesis using cloud-based e-learning model and those taught using conventional method.
2. There is no significant difference in the mean achievement score of male and female Biology students taught the concept of photosynthesis using Cloud-based e-learning model.

RESEARCH METHOD

This study adopted a quasi-experimental, pretest-posttest, non-randomized design. The study was conducted in the Mkpato Enin Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. The population consisted of all 1,754 Senior Secondary one (SS1) Biology students from the 16 public co-educational secondary schools in the study area during the 2025/2026 academic session. The sample size comprised 97 SS1 Biology students in two intact classes from the two secondary schools in the study area selected using a simple random sampling technique. In each of the selected schools, one intact class of SS1 Biology students was randomly assigned to Experimental Group 1 (taught using Cloud-based e-learning model) and Control Group 1 (taught using conventional method) respectively. One instrument was used in gathering data for the study, viz: a 20- item 4-option multiple choice test with four options (A-D) tagged: Biology Achievement Test on Photosynthesis (BAP), designed to measure the pre-test and post-test achievement in the concept of photosynthesis in Biology. To ensure face and content validity, the instrument was submitted to three independent assessors, two content experts in Biology education and one expert in Research Measurement and Evaluation, all in the Faculty of Education, Akwa Ibom State University, Mkpato Enin. The reliability of the BAP was determined using the Kuder-Richardson formula - 20 (KR-20), with a reliability coefficient of 0.86. Data were analyzed using mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions, while analysis of covariance was used to test the hypotheses at a 0.05 level of significance.

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RESULTS

Research Question One: What is the difference in the mean achievement score of students taught the concept of photosynthesis using Cloud-based e-learning model and those taught using conventional method?

Table 1: Mean and standard deviation of achievement scores of students on pretest and posttest based on teaching methods

Teaching Methods	N	Pretest Mean	SD	Posttest Mean	SD	Mean Gain
Cloud-based e-learning model	45	7.18	1.54	17.33	3.11	10.15
Conventional Method	52	7.31	2.02	14.42	3.15	7.11

The results in Table 1 show that students taught the concept of photosynthesis using the Cloud-based e-learning model had a pretest mean score of 7.18 (SD = 1.54), which increased substantially to a posttest mean score of 17.33 (SD = 3.11), resulting in a mean gain of 10.15. In contrast, students taught using the conventional method recorded a pretest mean score of 7.31 (SD = 2.02) and a posttest mean score of 14.42 (SD = 3.15), with a mean gain of 7.11. Although both teaching methods improved students' achievement, the mean gain of students exposed to the Cloud-based e-learning model (10.15) was higher than that of those taught using the conventional method (7.11). This indicates that while both methods were effective, the Cloud-based e-learning model produced greater improvement in students' academic achievement in photosynthesis.

Research Question Two: What is the difference in the mean achievement score of male and female Biology students taught the concept of photosynthesis using Cloud-based e-learning model?

Table 2: Mean and standard deviation of students' achievement scores by gender and teaching method

Teaching Method	Gender	N	Pretest Mean	SD	Posttest Mean	SD	Mean Gain
Cloud-based e-learning model	Male	16	7.50	2.00	17.75	3.15	10.25
	Female	29	7.00	1.22	17.10	3.12	10.10
Conventional Method	Male	19	7.47	1.90	14.95	3.42	7.48
	Female	33	7.21	2.10	14.12	3.00	6.91

Table 2 reveals that under the Cloud-based e-learning model, male students improved from a pretest mean of 7.50 (SD = 2.00) to a posttest mean of 17.75 (SD = 3.15), yielding a mean gain of 10.25, while female students improved from 7.00 (SD = 1.22) to 17.10 (SD = 3.12), with a mean gain of 10.10. This indicates that both male and female students benefited substantially from the Cloud-based e-learning model, with male students showing a slightly higher gain. Under the conventional method, male students increased from a pretest mean of 7.47 (SD = 1.90) to a posttest mean of 14.95 (SD = 3.42), resulting in a mean gain of 7.48, while female students improved from 7.21 (SD = 2.10) to 14.12 (SD = 3.00), with a mean gain of 6.91. Overall, both teaching methods enhanced achievement for male and female students, with the Cloud-based e-learning model yielding higher gains across both genders and only minimal gender differences observed.

Hypothesis One: There is no significant difference in the mean achievement score of students taught the concept of photosynthesis using Cloud-based e-learning model and those taught using conventional method.

Table 3: Result of Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) on the difference in mean achievement scores based on teaching methods

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	225.078	2	112.539	11.600	.000
Intercept	1762.766	1	1762.766	181.702	.000
Pretest	20.760	1	20.760	2.140	.147
Teaching Methods	199.377	1	199.377	20.551	.000*
Error	911.932	94	9.701		
Total	25270.000	97			
Corrected Total	1137.010	96			

○ *R Squared = .198 (Adjusted R Squared = .181)*
Significant @0.05 level of significance

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The ANCOVA result in Table 3 indicates that the effect of teaching methods on students' mean achievement scores is statistically significant, $F(1,94) = 20.551, p = .000 < .05$. Since the probability value is less than the 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis is rejected. This implies that a significant difference exists in the mean achievement scores of students taught photosynthesis using the Cloud-based e-learning model and those taught using the conventional method. The difference favours the Cloud-based e-learning model, as students exposed to it recorded a higher mean gain (10.15) compared to those taught using the conventional method (7.11).

Hypothesis Two: There is no significant difference in the mean achievement score of male and female Biology students taught the concept of photosynthesis using Cloud-based e-learning model.

Table 4: Result of Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) on the difference in mean achievement scores based on gender

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	40.874	2	20.437	1.753	.179
Intercept	1789.734	1	1789.734	153.480	.000
Pretest	29.519	1	29.519	2.531	.115
Gender	15.173	1	15.173	1.301	.257
Error	1096.136	94	11.661		
Total	25270.000	97			
Corrected Total	1137.010	96			

a. R Squared = .036 (Adjusted R Squared = .015)

The ANCOVA result in Table 4 shows that the effect of gender on students' mean achievement scores is not statistically significant, $F(1,94) = 1.301, p = .257 > .05$. Since the p-value is greater than 0.05, the null hypothesis is retained. This indicates that there is no significant difference in the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught photosynthesis using the Cloud-based e-learning model when pretest scores are controlled. Thus, gender did not significantly influence students' academic achievement.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The findings revealed that students taught photosynthesis using the Cloud-based e-learning model achieved significantly higher scores than those taught using the conventional method. The higher mean gain observed among students exposed to the Cloud-based approach suggests that features such as accessibility, flexibility, and resource sharing enhanced learning. This outcome may be attributed to the ability of cloud-based platforms to provide learning materials at any time and place, thereby improving engagement and understanding. This finding agrees with Amir (2025), who noted that e-learning offers advantages such as reduced cost, flexibility, and improved access to learning resources. Similarly, Wu and Plakhtii (2021) asserted that cloud-based e-learning improves students' academic achievement through updated technologies and learning tools, while Alam (2021) reported a significant relationship between e-learning models and students' achievement in Biology.

The study also found that there was no significant difference in the achievement of male and female students taught using the Cloud-based e-learning model. Although slight differences in mean gains were observed, these differences were not statistically significant. This suggests that the Cloud-based learning environment provided equal learning opportunities for both genders. The interactive and learner-centered nature of the model may have minimized gender-related disparities in learning outcomes. This finding is consistent with Umanah and Akpan (2024) and Umanah and Sunday (2022), who reported no significant gender difference in students' academic performance. It also supports the findings of Sunday, Edet and Akpan (2025), Sunday et al., (2025) and Ntegwung et al., (2026), who found that gender does not significantly influence achievement in science subjects. Overall, the results imply that while Cloud-based e-learning significantly enhances students' achievement in photosynthesis, it does so equitably across gender. This suggests that integrating cloud-based technologies into Biology instruction can improve learning outcomes without introducing gender bias, thereby supporting inclusive and effective science education.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of the study, it is concluded that cloud-based e-learning model significantly enhanced students' academic achievement in the concept of photosynthesis compared to the conventional teaching method. Cloud-based e-learning model allows students to carry out face-to-face tasks supplemented by a range of online resources to fully online courses without time limit and

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as well improve students critical thinking and innovation. These findings underscore the importance of adopting innovative teaching strategies in Biology education to improve student engagement and learning outcomes. Finally, the teaching strategies were gender-friendly, providing equitable learning opportunities for all students.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings, the following recommendations were made:

1. Biology teachers should adopt cloud-based e-learning model teaching method to enhance the teaching and learning of photosynthesis and other Biology concepts.
2. Curriculum planners should incorporate innovative pedagogical strategies, such as cloud-based e-learning model teaching strategy among others into the biology curriculum for the teaching of photosynthesis and other abstract concepts in biology. This will ensure that these teaching methods are widely adopted and standardized.
3. Pre-service teachers should be trained on how to create and utilize cloud-based e-learning model for teaching Biology concepts.

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